

KU LEUVEN

MATERIALS ENGINEERING

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Composite
Materials
Group

Bamboo fibre composites – moisture resistant and durable

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Sustainable material utilisation; Life cycle energy consumption of different products (according to Ashby)

Need
Light-weight:
Carbon or natural fibre

Need low embedded energy:
Natural fibre !

Can natural fibres be even better than traditional composite fibres?

Embedded energy is low; especially relevant for building & construction

Some data on energy utilisation for fibre production:

European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

Bio-based bridge

Natural Fibres; classification

Natural Fibre Composites; Mechanical performance

Specific tensile modulus E/ρ (MJ/kg) for various fibres

Material stiffness efficiency in tension

Specific FLEXURAL modulus $(E(1/3)/\rho)$ in $N(1/3)m(7/3)/kg$ for various fibres

Material efficiency in (plate) bending (or buckling)

Natural fibre composite specific properties

Specific tensile stiffness (E/ρ) in (MJ/kg) for various materials; composites are 0/90 composites with $V_f = 50$ vol%

Material stiffness efficiency in tension

Specific bending stiffness ($E(1/3)/\rho$) in ($N(1/3)m(7/3)/kg$) for various materials; composites are 0/90 composites with $V_f = 50$ vol%

Material efficiency in (plate) bending (or buckling)

Natural Fibre Composites; Strengths and weaknesses

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
Renewability	Moisture sensitivity / Durability ✓
Low Carbon footprint	Variability? ✓
Moderate cost	Not-optimized interfaces ✓
Low abrasiveness	Thermal degradation ✓
Healthier?	Non-linear stress-strain behaviour? ✓
Good specific mechanical properties (longitudinally)	Low transverse and shear properties ✓
Acoustic and vibrational damping	Water during processing ✓
Low CTE	Not optimized fibre preforms ✓
Natural look and feel	Extraction without damage ✓

Main challenges for Bio-based Composites

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Ways to improve Durability, particularly moisture sensitivity

- 1) Choose less moisture sensitive natural fibres, e.g. bamboo fibre
- 2) Lower the Equilibrium Moisture Content (EMC) of the fibres; chemical treatment (EU H2020 BBI Ssuchy)
- 3) Reduce the swelling of the fibres; constraint from the matrix? (EU Marie Curie FibreNet)
- 4) Turn water inside the fibres into an advantage, process with water inside the fibres; pre-swollen fibres (Ssuchy)
- 5) Coatings (of fibres or composite); slow down water diffusion and mitigate peak loads (Ssuchy)

Bamboo Fibre Extraction

Introduction Bamboo fibre composites

- Bamboo fibres have excellent mechanical properties
- Specific properties comparable to glass fibre
- Bamboo can grow to 20 m in 6 months
- Can fix up to 50 tons of C/ha.year
- Challenge is to extract technical fibres

Culm with vascular bundles

Technical fibre(s)

Elementary fibres

Exploded view of a bamboo plant

Why bamboo ?

Abundant supply

15 million hectares of giant bamboo, suited for composite applications

Renewable

Can be harvested every year without depletion of the soil

Yield up to 20-30 ton biomass/ hectare => 1-3 ton of bamboo fibres

Harvest starting from year 3

Diverse plant

Over 1600 species are known, adapts easily

Ecological benefits

No fertilisation needed

Can be grown on degraded land, landscape restoration

CO2 Sequestration

Moisture sensitivity of technical bamboo fibres

20%RH

80%RH

Moisture Sensitivity of Bamboo Composites

(epoxy matrix)

Moisture sensitivity of bamboo fibre composites

Modulus does not decrease much!

(Epoxy matrix, Vf 40%)

PhD Lina Osorio

UD FLAX composite:

Relating chemical composition to water take-up

	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Crystallinity (%)	EMC* (%)
Flax	92.0 ± 0.7	5.6 ± 0.7	2.5 ± 0.1	50.0	7.4
Coir	48.1 ± 1.3	16.5 ± 1.5	35.4 ± 0.7	35.4	10.0
Hemp	89.6 ± 1.2	7.4 ± 0.5	3.0 ± 0.6	63.0	8.5
Jute	69.2 ± 0.6	16.4 ± 0.4	14.3 ± 0.3	57.5	9.7
Spruce	55.4 ± 0.1	16.9 ± 0.3	27.7 ± 0.4	41.5	10.7
Bamboo	66.3 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.5	23.7 ± 0.9	51.0	9.7

*In the desorption cycle, RH 50%

$$\begin{aligned} EMC @RH50, desorption (experimental) = & \\ & 0.183 (\text{amount of } \mathbf{amorphous} \text{ cellulose}) + \\ & 0.546 (\text{amount of hemicellulose}) \\ & + 0.004 (\text{amount of lignin}) \end{aligned}$$

PhD Delphine Depuydt,
2018

Retention of properties after artificial ageing

Cycling was done at 80°C between 1.2 % RH (oven) and 80 % RH

Aged samples tested in fully dried state after a short re-equilibration to room temperature

Tensile strength of cycled composites for the reference specimens (after manufacturing) and after 5 cycles (ultimate tensile strength normalised to V_f 40 %)

- C1, C2, C3 refers to level of **cleanliness**, with C3 having the lowest amount of residual parenchyma.
- Also clean fibres lose strength; remediation by fibre treatment or working with pre-swollen damp fibres

Bamboo fibre process development

Problem statement

Node

Internode

Discontinuity of the fibre

Length of internodes
(± 25 cm)

UD prepreg with discontinuous fibres; continuous process?

Continuous UD prepreg

Discontinuous UD prepreg

UD bamboo fibre-thermoplastic tape

WO 2018-134324

Bamboo fibre developing the value chain

Project Bamboo Value Chain

PhD Delphine Depuydt
2018

* Bamboo sourced from Columbia, Vietnam, Europe

Developing the value chain (“bio-refinery”)

Products coming to market

- * Short bamboo fibre preform and prepreg
- * Long fibres and continuous yarn

Compressive properties of natural fibre composites

	Flax Tensile properties	Flax Compressive properties	Ratio (%)	Bamboo Tensile properties	Bamboo Compressive properties	Ratio (%)
Strength (MPa)	222,9 ± 6,1	136,9 ± 5,5	61	254,7 ± 18,3	149,5 ± 8,9	59
Modulus (GPa)	23,9 ± 1,9	15,1 ± 2,5	63	19,5 ± 1,0	15,5 ± 2,7	79

CMG expertise: Studying and improving the Fibre Matrix Interface; Durability enhancement (Dr. Carlos Fuentes)

- An integrated physical-chemical-micromechanical approach

1) Physical characterization: surface energy components from contact angle measurements

$$\gamma_{L,i}(1 + \cos\theta_i) = 2(\sqrt{\gamma_{L,i}^{LW} \gamma_S^{LW}} + \sqrt{\gamma_{L,i}^+ \gamma_S^-} + \sqrt{\gamma_{L,i}^- \gamma_S^+})$$

2) Surface chemistry: XPS, ToF-SIMS

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

3) (Micro)-mechanical testing of adhesion

(single fibre pull-out & transverse UD 3-point bending)

Tools for selecting fibre treatment or matrix modification

For improvement of wetting and adhesion

Bamboo fibre surface analysis

XPS results; courtesy C. DuPont, UCL

C1/C ratios versus O/C ratios for chemical groups at the surface of bamboo fibres

Bean-shaped fibre zone breaks up in various technical fibres upon extraction

Extracted bamboo fibre surface seems to be *covered with lignin*

Work of adhesion versus interface & composite strength

Selecting the optimum thermoplastic matrix by matching surface energy components

Work of Adhesion

$$= \gamma_s + \gamma_l - \gamma_{sl}$$

Material	$W_a \left(\frac{mN}{m} \right)$
MAX	92
PVDF	78
MAPP	66
PP	68

Strength efficiency:

47 ↑ 60%

Transverse UD flexural strength for bamboo fibre composites

Longitudinal UD flexural strength for bamboo fibre composites

Interface strength – Transverse 3 point bending test

Effect of physical adhesion

Results of Surface Energy Component matching

Bamboo fibre UD composites

Matrix: PP and PVDF (+ some treatments)

Conclusions

Bamboo fibre has great potential as reinforcement fibre for composites

- Bamboo fibre = natural glass fibre
- Only 10% stiffness decay from 50 to 90 %RH (flax = 50% decay)
- Good environmental footprint
- But supply chain needs to be built
- And need for application-ready semi-finished products, like bamboo fibre tape

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